

Use of Phenolic Acids in the Detection, Separation and Estimation of Metals. Part II.

Colorimetric Detection and Estimation of Uranium.

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At present of all the existing methods* for the detection and estimation of minute quantities of uranium, the sodium salicylate method of Müller stands superior to every other method regarding its sensitiveness. It has however been found that the addition of tannic and gallic acids followed by sodium acetate produced remarkable coloration in uranium solution, which is more sensitive than the sodium salicylate test. As a solution of pyrogallic acid with sodium acetate, on standing, acquires a brown coloration, the detection and estimation were not possible with it; on the other hand, tannic acid with an excess of sodium acetate produces a gelatinous precipitate and hence the colorimetric estimation of uranium by means of tannic acid could not be carried on using excess of sodium acetate.

The phenolic acids, such as tannic, gallic and resorcylic, with dilute uranium solution only produced slight brownish coloration; to these on the addition of sodium acetate the color greatly intensified and became brown. The color produced in each case was not of the same intensity but in the increasing order: tannic, gallic, resorcylic.

In concentrated uranium salt solutions tannic acid produced a red-brown coloration and a partial chocolate brown precipitate. By the addition of sodium acetate to its filtrate, the color was intensified; with an excess of sodium acetate the whole of the uranium

* Colorimetric detection of uranium in minerals by potassium ferrocyanide—Bruttini, *Gazzetta*, 1893, (i) 23, 253.

Detection of minute quantities of uranium by hydrogen peroxide—Fairly, *Chem. News*, 1890, 62, 227 (0·85—0·25 mg. detectable).

Detection of uranium by ethylenediamine—Siemssen, *Chem. Zeit.*, 1911, 36, 139 (sensitiveness as that of hydrogen peroxide and potassium ferrocyanide methods).

Qualitative test of uranium by zinc in presence of nitric acid—Buell, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 598 (0·88 mg. per c.c. detectable).

Detection and estimation by sodium salicylate—Müller, *Chem. Zeit.*, 1919 43, 739 (0·2 per cent. of the metal estimable).

was precipitated and the filtrate was found to be colorless. Gallic and resorcylic acids in concentrated uranium solutions produced red-brown and brown colorations respectively but no precipitate. An addition of sodium acetate in excess to the mixtures increased the colorations; when however it was left for 2-3 hours, the formation of a gelatinous brown precipitate was observed in the case of gallic acid only. With a very concentrated uranium solution, gallic acid produced red-brown coloration and a precipitate.

The color reaction is more sensitive in uranium salt solution if sodium acetate is added after the addition of phenolic acids, but if the order of addition of these reagents be reversed, the color development is far less intense. It was also observed that the intensity of the color produced was proportional to the amount of uranium present in the solution, the color disappearing on adding dilute mineral acids and acetic acid.

The effect of salts as ammonium chloride, sodium phosphate, potassium pyrosulphate, Rochelle's salt and ammonium fluoride, which are likely to be present in the uranium solution in analyses, was studied. It was found that only in presence of ammonium chloride, the detection (but not the estimation) was possible by means of the phenolic acids.

It is thus evident that the colorimetric estimation of uranium is suitable purely in its neutral solution by tannic, gallic or resorcylic acid and sodium acetate. When uranium is present in acetic, hydrochloric or nitric acid solution, the estimation may be carried out by driving off the acid, or by neutralising the acid solution with caustic soda or better with ammonia. According to Müller, neutral alkali salts do not interfere in the estimation of uranium by sodium salicylate but it was found that potassium chloride imparted a greenish tinge to the original reddish-yellow color and increased its intensity. Hence the estimation in presence of a neutral alkali salt is rather faulty. It was also found that with the increasing amount of sodium salicylate a gradual greenish tinge developed in the solution with increasing intensity. Comparing Müller's with the author's method of estimation, the respective sensitiveness stands in the order: Tannic acid > gallic acid > sodium salicylate > resorcylic acid. It was found that with 0.2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid and 3 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate, 0.0115 gm. of uranium per litre could be detected and 0.023 gm. per litre could be accurately estimated. With 2 c.c. of about 1 per cent. gallic acid and 1 c.c. of 5 per cent.

sodium acetate, the detectable amount of uranium is 0.0233 gm. per litre and its estimable amount is 0.0345 g. per litre, whereas with resorcylic acid, the detectable lower limit is 0.069 gm. and with 8 per cent. sodium salicylate, the detectable amount and the estimable amounts are 0.046 gm. per litre.

In estimating uranium, fresh solutions of the acids were always used. The reagents were added in the standard and in the unknown solutions simultaneously and the colorations were immediately compared, as, on standing for a long time, the coloration is affected by the air. In actual estimation it was found that when the volumes of the uranium solution for comparison were not widely different, then using 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid and 1 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate, satisfactory results were obtained. But with widely varying volumes of uranium solutions considerable discrepancies in the results were noticed; the solution containing greater amount of uranium showed less color intensity. By trial, it was found that in very condition, best results were obtained by using 3 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate instead of 1 c.c. This may be due to the fact that using 3 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate with 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid, the mixture comes to a neutral range, and hence the maximum color production. With the idea of verifying this by p_H measurements, it was found that the p_H of 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid made up to 10 c.c. with conductivity water was 3-3.5; that of 2 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate was 8.7-8.9; and of the uranium nitrate solution (1 c.c. = 0.00023 g. per litre) was 4.3. The p_H of uranium nitrate and tannic acid (1 to 8 c.c. of uranium solutions and 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid made up to 10 c.c.) was 2.8-3.

Now the cause of maximum color-effect could have been easily ascertained, if the p_H change in the mixture of uranium solution and tannic acid by the gradual addition of 5 per cent. sodium acetate, could be measured; but as a coloration was produced by the addition of sodium acetate, the measurement was not possible by using indicators. However by taking small volumes of uranium solution (0.5-1 c.c.) and adding to this 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid followed by 5 per cent. sodium acetate (1-5 c.c.) it was found that with 3 c.c. of sodium acetate solution the p_H in every case was 6.0 to 6.05.

The color-effect was also studied by keeping the proportions of uranium nitrate, tannic acid and sodium acetate constant and

changing the p_H by Buffer's solutions and the maximum color-effect was produced at p_H 6.1.

It is seen that in p_H 6.1 maximum color-effect is produced and excess of tannic acid or sodium acetate can produce no more color-effect; but with excess of sodium acetate after 8 to 10 minutes the mixture becomes colloidal. From the behaviour of excess of sodium acetate it can also be said that the cause of maximum color formation is purely a case of colloid formation. Tannic acid with uranium solution forms some sort of compound which remains in solution in colloidal and dissociated state, and the solution is feebly acidic. Sodium acetate neutralises the acid and helps the association and then coagulation. The amount of sodium acetate causing the maximum association of uranium with tannic acid, being capable of remaining in solution, evidently gives maximum color effect and is the important factor in the estimation. In the estimations with gallic acid or resorcylic acid no such difficulties, as in the case of tannic acid, are encountered. In all the cases the comparison of colors is made under similar conditions. The estimations with gallic acid gave most satisfactory results. The estimation with resorcylic acid and also its sensitiveness in comparison with those of tannic and gallic acids are not at all satisfactory. The comparison of colors in the estimations was made in a dipping colorimeter. Comparison in Nessler's tubes also gives good results.

When uranium solution is treated with an excess of tannic acid and an excess of sodium acetate, or with excess of tannic acid ammonium acetate and a drop of dilute ammonia, a quantitative precipitation of uranium is obtained, which on ignition gives U_3O_8 . This observation leads to gravimetric method for the estimation of uranium (*vide* Part III).

EXPERIMENTAL.

About 5 g. of uranyl nitrate were dissolved in 250 c.c. of water, and in 25 c.c. of it, uranium was estimated as U_3O_8 by freshly prepared ammonia. Thus the solution contained 0.28 gm. of uranium per 25 c.c. 25 C.c. of this solution were diluted to 100 c.c. and in this solution uranium was estimated colorimetrically by the phenolic acids.

Tannic Acid and Sodium Acetate.

Qualitative Lower Limit.—0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 c.c. of the dilute uranium solution were taken in five test tubes and water was

added to each, such that with 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid (freshly prepared) and 1 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate the volume was 10 c.c. in each case. To a 6th one 7 c.c. of water were taken and tannic acid and sodium acetate were added as before. Then the effect in each of the five test tubes was compared with that of the 6th one.

No.	Observation.	Remarks.
1st.	Light-brown coloration noticeable at the meniscus.	The color production nearly the same
2nd.	" "	"
3rd.	" "	Color production more intense than in the 1st or 2nd.
4th.	Color production in the body of the solution, but more pronounced at the meniscus.	Very faint.
5th.	" "	Fairly perceptible and more intense than in the 4th.
6th.	Colorless solution, extremely faint, yellowish coloration at meniscus.	

Hence the lowest amount of uranium that can be detected by tannic acid and sodium acetate is $0.000023 \times 5 = 0.000115$ g. in 10 c.c. i.e., 0.0115 g. per litre.

By using 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid and 3 c.c. of 5 per cent. sodium acetate (the proportion for ideal condition) the same observations were noticed.

Quantitative Estimation.—As even 2 per cent. solution of tannic acid is brownish in color and strong solutions of tannic acid are more acted on by the air producing deep brown solutions, so, for the estimation, 1 per cent. solution, which has a slight brownish tinge, is perfectly suitable. It has been found that 2 c.c. of this 1 per cent. solution diluted to 10 c.c. with water show no brownish tinge. Hence in the estimations always 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. tannic acid solution are used. Fairly strong solutions of sodium acetate produce a while turbidity or a gelatinous precipitate with tannic acid, hence a weak solution (5 per cent.) is used, which is found to be satisfactory.

In two comparison tubes of a dipping colorimeter, measured volumes of dilute uranium solution were taken and water was added, such that with 2 c.c. of the tannic acid and 1 c.c. of the sodium-

acetate solution, the volume was 10 c.c. in each case. Now by fixing one of the tube at a definite scale reading and sliding the other up and down, the color intensity of the one was matched with the other. The readings are tabulated below:—

Experiment 1.

		Tube R—2 c.c. uranium solution.							
		,, L—3 c.c. ,, ,,							
Readings	R ..30	30	30	20	20	10	10	10	10
	L...21	20'8	21	14'1	14'0	7	7	7	7
Remarks	f...Yellow.			Yellowish.				Almost white.	
	r...19'5-22'5			13-15'2				6'4-7'6	
Readings	R...5	5	5	7'4	7'3	14'1	14'1		
	L...3'5	3'4	3'4	5	5	10	10		
Remarks	f...White.			White.				Yellowish.	
	r...2'7-4'0			6'4-7'8				13'0-15'0	

R—Right hand side tube and

L—Left hand side tube of the calorimeter.

f—Color of the match-field.

r—The range within which the intensity of the color in the two fields begins to appear almost the same, *i.e.*, within which the match point lies.

Experiment 2.

		Tube R—3 c.c. uranium solution.							
		,, L—4 c.c. ,, ,,							
Readings	R ..30	30	30	20	20	10	10	10	10
	L ..22'2	22'7	22'5	14'5	15	7'6	7'8	7'7	7'5
Remarks	f...Yellow.			Yellowish.				Almost white.	
	r.. 20'8-23'6			13'4-15'7				7'0-8'0	

Experiment 3.

		Tube R—6 c.c. uranium solution.							
		,, L—7 c.c. ,, ,,							
Readings	R...10	10	5	5	5	6	5'8	5'9	
	L...8'7	8'3	4'1	4'3	4'2	5	5	5	
Remarks	f...Slight yellowish.			Almost white.				Almost white.	

From the experiments it is seen that good results are obtained when the match field is almost white; as this enables one to detect a sharp change in the field of comparison.

Experiment 4.

	Tube R—2 c.c. uranium solution.					
	,, L—6 c.c.		,,		,,	
Readings	R ..30	30	20	20	10	10
	L ..11·7	11·5	7·7	7·7	3·8	3·8
Remarks	f...Yellow.		Yellowish.		Almost white.	
	r...11·12·2		7·0·8·1		3·2·4·2	

Experiment 5.

	Tube R—1 c.c. uranium solution.					
	,, L—3 c.c.		,,		,,	
Readings	R ..30	30	20	20	20	10 10
	L...11·8	11·7	7·6	7·7	7·9	3·6 3·7
Remarks	f...Light yellow.		Almost white.		White.	
	r...10·5-12·6		6·7-8·6		2·7-4·4	

Experiment 6.

	Tube R—2 c.c. uranium solution.					
	,, L—7 c.c.		,,		,,	
Readings	R . 25	25	20	20	15	15 10 10
	L ..10·7	10·7	8·7	8·7	6·5	6·6 4·5 4·4
Remarks	f...Yellowish.		Yellowish tinge.		Almost white. White.	
	r...10·0-12·0		8·0-10·0		6·0-7·5 3·7-4·7	

From the readings of the Expts. 4, 5 and 6 it is seen that L's with comparatively higher amounts of uranium than the R's show weaker color-effect than that expected. As the match point is very sharp, *i.e.*, within 1—1·2 scale reading and it is likely that with so much uranium the color is not fully developed, so to get maximum color development either more tannic acid solution or more sodium acetate requires to be added. Whereas in Experiments 1, 2 and 3 with closer amounts of uranium the color-effects in two cases cannot materially effect the estimation. By numerous trials the

ideal conditions, which give good results, are to use 2 c.c. of 1% tannic acid and 3 c.c. of 5% sodium acetate solution and the results thereof are given below. In these cases also the volumes of the solution for comparison are 10 c.c.

Experiment 7.

		Tube R—3 c.c. uranium solution.										
		,, L—5 c.c. ,, ,,					,, ,, ,, ,, ,,					
Readings	R...30	30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10	10		
	L...18	18	14.8	14.9	11.9	11.9	8.8	8.9	5.8	6.0		
Remarks	f...	Deep yellow.	Yellow.		Yellow.		Light yellow.		Yellowish.			
	r...	17.2-18.8	14.2-15.8		11.4-12.6		8.3-9.6		5.6-6.4			

Experiment 8.

		Tube R—1 c.c. uranium solution.										
		,, L—3 c.c. ,, ,,					,, ,, ,, ,, ,,					
Readings	R...30	30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10	10		
	L...10.8	10.8	9	8.9	7.4	7.3	5.5	5.5	3.3	3.4		
Remarks	f...	Light yellow.	Yellowish.		Almost white.		White.		White.			
	r...	10.2-11.8	8.6-9.7		6.7-7.8		5.0-6.0		2.9-3.9			

Experiment 9.

		Tube R—2 c.c. uranium solution.										
		,, L—3 c.c. ,, ,,					,, ,, ,, ,, ,,					
Readings	R...30	30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10	10		
	L...20.4	20.5	17.8	17.8	13.6	13.5	10.3	10.2	6.7	6.7		
Remarks	f...	Yellow.	Yellow.		Yellowish.		Yellowish.		Almost white.			
	r...	19.4-21.5	16.6-18.8		12.7-14.4		9.7-10.9		6.2-7.3			

In all the experiments it is seen that when the match field is white or almost white, the range is small and the results of comparison are more accurate. So, for comparison, always white or almost white field should be brought about.

Maximum Color Development under the Ideal Condition.—The probable causes of the maximum color production have been discussed before. However, in support of the cause due to p_H , another

point is noticed as follows: studying the p_H values of uranium solution and sodium acetate it is observed that 1 c.c. uranium solution + 1 c.c. sodium acetate made up to 10 c.c. with water give p_H 6.9 and 3 c.c. uranium solution + 3 c.c. sodium acetate made up to the same volume give p_H 6.9; so it is expected that with 2 c.c. tannic acid in each case there should be produced a color-effect in the ratio of 1:3, and actually this is the case.

Experiment 10.

	U soln.			Sodium acetate.			Water.		Tannic acid.		
	R—1 c.c.			1 c. c.			6 c.c.		2 c.c.		
	L—3 c.c.			3 c.c.			2 c.c.		2 c.c.		
Readings	R...30	30	30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10	10
	L...10.3	10.1	10	8.7	8.5	6.9	7.0	5.1	5.2	3.4	3.5
Remarks	f..Yellowish.			Yellowish	Almost white.	Almost white.	White.				
	r...9.6-11.0			tinge. 8.0-9.3	6.6-7.6	4.7-5.7	3.0-4.0				

Experiment 11.

Tube R—0.5 c.c. uranium solution.

„ L—1.0 c.c. „ „

Readings	R...30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10
	L...16.9	14.1	14.4	11.8	11.5	8.7	8.9	5.6

Experiment 12.

Tube R—0.5 c.c. uranium solution.

„ L—0.6 c.c. „ „

Readings	R...30	30	25	26	20	20	15	10	10
	L...25.4	25.0	21.2	21.3	17.0	17.3	12.4	8.4	8.5
	r...24.3-27.3	19.0-22.0	15.8-18.6	11.0-13.7	7.4-10.0				

Experiment 13.

Tube R—1.0 c.c. uranium solution.

„ L—1.5 c.c. „ „

Readings	R...30	30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10	10
	L...20.2	20.5	17	17	13.4	13.6	10.2	10.2	7.0	6.9
	r...19-21	16.4-18	13.8-14.6							

From the above experiments it is seen that with 1 c.c. of the uranium solution (0.00023 g. U) the estimation is most satisfactory. In Expt. 12, however, good results are obtained, but the range is greater. So 0.00023 g. of uranium in 10 c.c., i.e., 0.023 g. per litre can be very well estimated.

Determination in Nessler's Colorimeter.

Tannic acid solution = 2 c.c.

Sodium acetate ,, = 3 c.c.

Expts.	Tubes.	U-soln. taken (c.c.)	Match point.		Found. (c.c.)	Taken.
			Water added. (c.c.)	Total vol. (c.c.)		
14	A	x	y	50	4.08	4.0 c.c.
	B	4	40	49		
15	A	x	y	50	3.4	3.5
	B	1.5	16.5	22		
16	A	x	y	50	2.94	3.0
	B	2	27	34		
17	A	x	y	100	5.26	5.5
	B	1	13	19		

Estimation in Presence of Acids.—To uranium solution, nitric or hydrochloric acid is added, the acid is driven off by repeated evaporation with little water. The residue is then taken up with water in a Nessler's tube (A); 2 c.c. tannic acid and 3 c.c. sodium acetate solutions are added, the volume is made up to 50 c.c. with water; the color in the tube thus produced is matched with the color by adding measured volumes of water in the other tube (B), where a known amount of uranium is present.

Expts.	Tubes.	U soln. taken. (c.c.)	Vols. at match- point (c.c.)	Found (c.c.)
18	A	2	50	1.97
	B	1.5	38	
19	A	3	50	2.94
	B	1	17	
20	A	3	50	3.03
	B	2	33	
21	A	4	50	4.17
	B	5	60	

Detection and Estimation by Means of Gallic Acid and Sodium Acetate.—In this case the limit is determined just as in the case of tannic acid using 2 c.c. 1% gallic acid and 1 c.c. 5% sodium acetate solutions and is found to be 0.023 g. per litre. But addition of ammonium chloride increases the sensitiveness.

Quantitative Estimation.—Under the following experimental conditions, as tabulated, readings are taken and are given below.

Expts.	Tubes.	U soln. (c.c.)	1 % Gallic acid (c.c.)	5% Sodium acetate. (c.c.)	Water. (c.c.)	Total vol. (c.c.)
22	R	2	2	4	2	10
	L	4	.		—	„
23	R	2	4	2	2	10
	L	4	4	2	—	„
24	R	2	2	1	5	„
	L	6	„	„	1	„
25	R	2.0	1.5	2	4.5	„
	L	6	„	„	0.5	„
26	R	1.5	2	2.0	4.5	„
	L	8	2	—	—	„

Corresponding readings :—

Expt. 22	R	30	20	20	10	10		
	L	15.8	15.4	10.3	19.2	5.2	5.1	
Expt. 23	R	30	20	20	10	10		
	L	15.8	15.4	10.3	10.2	5.2	5.1	
Expt. 24	R	30	30	25	25	20	20	15 15
	L	9.9	9.9	8.3	8.4	6.7	6.8	4.8 5.0
Expt. 25	R	30	30	25	25	20	20	15 15
	L	10.0	9.9	8.2	8.4	9.7	6.6	5.0 5.0
Expt. 26	R	30	30	25	25	20	20	
	L	7.4	7.5	6.5	6.5	5.1	5.1	

In all these experiments the range is within one division of scale reading.

Estimation in Presence of Ammonium Chloride.

Expts.	Tubes.	U soln. (c.c.)	NH ₄ Cl soln. (c.c.)	1% Gallic acid. (c.c.)	5% Sodium acetate. (c.c.)	Water. (c.c.)	Total vol. (c.c.)
27	{ R ..	2	2	2	2	4	12
	{ L ..	6	"	"	"	—	"
28	{ R ..	2	2	2	2	2	10
	{ L ..	6	—	2	2	—	"

Corresponding readings :—

Expt. 27	{ R...	30	30	25	25	20	20	15	15	10	10
	{ L...	10.2	10.1	8.7	8.5	6.8	6.8	5.0	5.1	3.5	3.3
Expt. 28	{ R...	30	30	20	20	10	10				
	{ L...	12.5	12.5	8.5	8.5	4.8	4.2				

From the readings of Expts. 27 and 28 it is clear that with ammonium chloride the color-effect is much increased than in the case where no ammonium chloride is used. But by adding the same amount of ammonium chloride the estimation is all right, as seen in Expt. 27. So in the presence of ammonium chloride (unknown amount) the estimation is not suitable. The only advantage of ammonium chloride is that it increases the sensitiveness.

Detection and Estimation with Resorcylic Acid and Sodium Acetate.—A faint yellow coloration is noticed in the body of 10 c.c. solution using 3 c.c. of the dilute uranium solution, i.e., 0.069 g. of uranium per litre is detectable. Under similar conditions (that is with 2 c.c. resorcylic acid and 1 c.c. sodium acetate, the total volume being 10 c.c.) to the following experiments are done. This shows that the estimation with resorcylic acid is not at all satisfactory for reasons of low sensitiveness and high range.

Expt.	Tubes.	U soln. (c.c.)					
29	{ R...	3	Readings	R...30	30	20	20
	{ L...	4		L...21	21	14.6	15.6
30	{ R...	5	Readings	r... 19.23		14.18	
	{ L...	4		R...25	25	20	20
	{ R...	5		L...29	29.2	23	22.5
	{ L...	4		r... 26.5-30		20.6-26	
31	{ R...	5	Readings	R...30	30	30	20
	{ L...	6		L...24.8	24	24.5	16.6
				r... 23-26		14.6-17.6	

Estimation with Sodium Salicylate: Effect of Neutral alkali Salt.

Expts.	Tubes.	U soln. (c.c.)	Water. (c.c.)	KCl soln.	Na-salicylate soln.	Total vol. (c.c.)
32	{ R	4	4	—	2 c.c. of 4%	10
	{ L	..	—	4 c.c. 20%
33	{ R	5	3	—	2 c.c. of 8%	..
	{ L	..	—	3 c.c. of 10%

Corresponding readings:—

Expt. 32	{ R...30	20	20	10		
	{ L...19	13.6	13	7.1		
Expt. 33	{ R...30	30	20	20	10	10
	{ L..26.2	26.7	17.9	18	9.0	9.1
	r ..26.2-27.6		17-19.4		8-10	

With potassium chloride the reddish-yellow color produced by sodium salicylate only is changed and a greenish shade is obtained, which causes a difficulty to get the match-point. But by adjusting the field to a white or almost white shade, somewhat accurate match-points were obtained. From Expts. 32 and 33 it is evident that the solution to which potassium chloride is added appears stronger and the more the potassium chloride in the solution, the more the color-effect.

Effect of Excess of Sodium Salicylate.—From several qualitative experiments and the comparison experiment given below it has been found that with excess of sodium salicylate the color with uranium solution intensifies, but a greenish tinge is imparted to the color, which renders the comparison very difficult.

Expt. 34	Tubes.	U soln.	Water.	Na-salicylate.	Total vol.	Remarks.
	{ R...	5 c.c.	3 c.c.	2 c.c. of 1%	10 c.c.	Reddish-yellow col.
	{ L..	2 c.c. of 8%	..	Greenish-yellow col.
Readings	{ R...	30	20	10		
	{ L...	No match pt. 5.6 (roughly adjusted)				

As with higher concentrations of sodium salicylate the color-effect is greater, so with 8% solution of sodium salicylate some determinations were carried out. In each case 2 c.c. of 8% sodium salicylate were added and the volume was made up to 10 c.c.

Expts. Tubes. U soln.

35	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{R...} \\ \text{L...} \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2 \text{ c.c.} \\ 5 \text{ c.c.} \end{array} \right.$	Readings	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{R...} \\ \text{L...} \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 19 \\ 3\cdot7 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \\ 3\cdot8 \end{array} \right.$	Remarks	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{f...White.} \\ \text{r...}2\cdot5\text{-}4\cdot7 \end{array} \right.$			
36	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{R...} \\ \text{L...} \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 3 \text{ c.c.} \\ 5 \text{ c.c.} \end{array} \right.$	Readings	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{R...} \\ \text{L...} \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 30 \\ 18\cdot3 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 30 \\ 18\cdot1 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 25 \\ 14\cdot5 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 25 \\ 14\cdot7 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 20 \\ 11\cdot8 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 20 \\ 11\cdot8 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \\ 5\cdot6 \end{array} \right.$
			Remarks	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{f...} \\ \text{r...} \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Yellowish.} \\ 17\text{-}19 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Yellowish} \\ 13\cdot7\text{-}15\cdot5 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{tinge.} \\ \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Almost;} \\ 10\cdot5\text{-}12\cdot2 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{White.} \\ 4\text{-}6 \end{array} \right.$		

After all it is seen that best results are obtained with gallic acid and sodium acetate.

The action of these phenolic acid has also been studied on other metallic salt solutions with successful results. Further work on the subject is in progress.

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